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Nanocarrier Systems for Violacein Delivery

Çağdaş Deniz PERİZ ^{1*}

¹ Suleyman Demirel University, Faculty of Engineering and Natural Sciences

Corresponding Author Email: denizperiz@gmail.com

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Abstract: Violacein is a natural microbial pigment predominantly produced by *Chromobacterium violaceum*, notable for its broad spectrum of biological activities. Despite its antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, anticancer, antiparasitic, and immunomodulatory properties, its hydrophobic nature and poor aqueous solubility represent major limitations to its bioavailability. Nanotechnological drug delivery systems have provided significant advances in overcoming these challenges. The literature reports numerous studies in which violacein has been incorporated into polymeric, lipid-based, metallic, and hybrid nanocarrier systems, leading to improved bioavailability, reduced toxicity, and enhanced controlled release profiles. Furthermore, synergistic antibacterial and anticancer effects have been achieved. This review summarizes the pharmaceutical potential of violacein, its solubility limitations, and the advantages conferred by nanotechnological carrier systems.

Introduction

Violacein is a violet pigment belonging to the indolocarbazole family, produced by *Chromobacterium violaceum* and *Janthinobacterium lividum* through quorum sensing (QS) mechanisms as a defensive strategy (Park et al., 2021). This pigment exhibits diverse biological properties, including antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, anticancer, antiulcerogenic, antiprotozoal, analgesic, and antipyretic activities. (Berti et al. 2019; Durán et al. 2003). Despite advancements in diagnostic and therapeutic strategies, including surgery, radiation, and chemotherapy, the development of novel, more effective, and less toxic anticancer agents remains a critical area of research (Bilici et al., 2025). Despite its valuable biological attributes, violacein demonstrates very low solubility in water and biological fluids, resulting in poor bioavailability. It is soluble in toxic organic solvents such as DMSO, methanol, ethanol, and ethyl acetate. (Gimenez et al., 2006). Therefore, the development of systems capable of enhancing its solubility in aqueous and biological environments, without reliance on toxic solvents, is of great significance for both in vitro and in vivo applications. Nanotechnology has long played a crucial role in the development of drug delivery systems. Loading drugs into nanocarriers provides several advantages, such as increased bioavailability, protection against enzymatic and pH degradation, reduction of toxic side effects, controlled release, and targeted delivery (Van Ngo et al., 2016).

Consequently, numerous recent studies have focused on incorporating violacein into various carrier materials to improve its bioavailability. A review of the literature reveals that although violacein has been studied for nearly 140 years, its remarkable properties, increasing potential applications across diverse industrial fields, applicability in controlled drug delivery systems, and the growing efforts to enhance production yield underscore its rising importance in recent years. The aim of this review is to highlight the biological effects of violacein, its solubility-related challenges, and the nanotechnological approaches developed to overcome these limitations. Given that the pharmaceutical potential of violacein remains constrained by its poor bioavailability, this study will discuss research focused on nanocarrier-based strategies to enhance its therapeutic performance. In doing so, the review intends to provide a comprehensive overview of current investigations while also identifying prospective research directions for future pharmaceutical and industrial applications.

Violacein Pigment

Violacein is a bisindole-derived, violet-colored bacterial pigment. It is produced by many Gram-negative bacteria, predominantly *Chromobacterium violaceum*, through quorum sensing (QS) mechanisms. The primary purpose of its production is to protect bacteria against natural enemies and various environmental stress factors. (Matz et al., 2008) The chemical structure of violacein is [3-(1,2-dihydro-5-(5-hydroxy-1H-indol-3-yl)-2-oxo-3H-pyrrol-3-yl)-1,3-dihydro-2H-indol-2-one], with a molecular weight of 343.342 g/mol. (Duran et al., 2021; Fávoro, et al., 2021). Violacein possesses numerous well-documented bioactive properties, including antibacterial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiparasitic, antiviral, antiprotozoal, and antifungal activities. Additionally, it exhibits synergistic effects when combined with several antibiotics. (Asencio et al., 2014). However, violacein is poorly soluble in water and is hydrophobic, which limits its direct biological applications (Choi et al., 2020). On the other hand, this hydrophobicity facilitates its extraction, as it dissolves well in toxic organic solvents (Berti et al., 2023).

Due to this limitation, recent studies have increasingly focused on combining violacein with various carrier systems to improve its solubility and expand its applicability in biological contexts. The advantages of violacein production include the ability to apply standard growth conditions, short production times, ease of cultivation, and low nutritional requirements. (Berti

et al., 2023). The antimicrobial activity of violacein against different strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is of particular importance, as these microorganisms are associated with a wide range of infections in mammals. (Asencio et al., 2014).

Moreover, violacein has been reported to demonstrate potent anticancer activity against several cancer types, including cervical, colon, bone, fibrosarcoma, neuroblastoma, breast, bladder, head and neck, and liver cancers. (Aires-Lopes et al., 2025; de Carvalho et al., 2006). Numerous studies in the literature have investigated the incorporation of violacein into nanocarrier systems to enhance its pharmacological potential. The aim of this review is to present the bioactive properties of this valuable pigment and to highlight studies that improve its solubility and thereby enhance its potential as a therapeutic agent.

Drug Delivery Applications

Nanocarriers are colloidal nanoparticles widely used for the delivery of drugs to target sites (Qian et al., 2012). With sizes ranging from 1 to 100 nanometers (nm) in diameter, nanocarriers can enhance drug efficacy by improving pharmacokinetics, bioavailability, and reducing toxicity. This is largely attributed to their high surface area-to-volume ratio (Mishra et al., 2010). Moreover, since drugs can be distributed within the nanometric matrix, solubility is no longer a limiting factor for therapeutic applications.

The modification of physicochemical properties of nanocarriers, including surface characteristics, composition and morphology, can enhance their activity while reducing adverse effects. This approach holds significant potential to create a major impact in the field of drug delivery (Sun et al., 2021). Nanocarriers exist in various forms, including organic, solid lipid, liposomes, dendrimers, polymeric nanoparticles, micelles, inorganic carriers, carbon nanotubes, gold nanoparticles, magnetic nanoparticles, quantum dots, mesoporous silica, and hybrid nanocarriers (Chamundeeswari et al., 2018).

The clinical success of nanocarriers in therapeutic applications has made them promising drug delivery platforms, offering opportunities for further improvement of overall drug delivery efficiency in the future.

Studies on Violacein-Loaded Nanocarriers

In the literature, numerous studies have reported the incorporation of violacein into different nanocarriers to improve its bioavailability. In one study, providing important insights into the molecular mechanisms of violacein's solubility and stability in aqueous environments, violacein-loaded nanoparticles were synthesized using sonication in the presence of SDS (Hamzah et al., 2024). Violacein-loaded chitosan–tripolyphosphate (CsTPP) nanoparticles synthesized by the ionic gelation method (149.0 nm, +23.40 mV zeta potential) have been proposed as safe additives, colorants, and therapeutic agents (Mohd et al., 2019).

In another study, silver nanoparticles coated with violacein (vAgNPs) and starch-coated silver nanoparticles (cAgNPs) were synthesized using a green method, and their antibacterial, antifungal, and antialgal activities were evaluated. vAgNPs demonstrated higher therapeutic efficacy and improved stability compared to cAgNPs. The results indicated that vAgNPs enhanced both the bioavailability and therapeutic effects of violacein (Arif et al., 2017). Nakazato et al. (2019) reported that the combination of violacein with biogenic silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) produced by *Fusarium Oxysporum* exhibited strong activity against resistant strains of *S. aureus*, an important pathogen in both humans and animals (Nakazato et al., 2019).

Choi et al. (2020) developed extracellular membrane vesicles to improve the solubility and delivery of violacein. After 6 hours of treatment with these vesicles, approximately 90% of

microorganisms were eliminated (Choi et al., 2020). Similarly, violacein-loaded poly(d,l-lactide-co-glycolide) nanoparticles were prepared to enhance solubility. These nanoparticles exhibited in vitro antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* ATCC 29213 and ATCC 25923 strains, with reduced MIC values compared to free violacein. However, in HL60 cells, nanoparticle-loaded violacein showed lower activity compared to free violacein (Martins et al., 2011). In contrast, Kanelli and colleagues encapsulated violacein together with superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles and polylactic acid nanoparticles. These formulations reduced cell viability by more than 80% in glioblastoma and melanoma cell lines. In another study, vio-Fe₃O₄-PLA nanoparticles were prepared, which effectively inhibited the growth of MRSA *S. aureus* (Kanelli et al., 2022).

Violacein-loaded nanoparticles were also developed using poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL), Tween 80, and chitosan via nanoprecipitation. These nanoparticles demonstrated lower MIC values against *S. aureus* compared to free violacein. Acute ecotoxicity tests using *Daphnia similis* showed that the nanoparticles had lower toxicity than free violacein. Additionally, CS_PCLnp-vio nanoparticles were reported to be more effective than free violacein in treating *S. aureus*-induced bovine mastitis infections (Berni et al., 2013)

Another study modified silk fabrics with violacein, followed by in situ synthesis of silver nanoparticles (SNPs), resulting in functional silk composites (FSCs) containing both violacein and SNPs. These composites exhibited strong synergistic antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Candida albicans*. While violacein alone reduced *S. aureus* by 81.25%, FSCs achieved reductions of 99.98%, 99.90%, and 99.85%, respectively, thereby broadening the antimicrobial spectrum (Gao et al., 2019).

Bioactive pigments extracted and purified from *Serratia marcescens* and *C. violaceum* cultures were combined with phytosynthesized silver and gold nanoparticles, and their effects on the in vitro growth of *Plasmodium falciparum* and *Trypanosoma brucei gambiense* were evaluated. Prodigiosin was found to be more effective than violacein in inhibiting both parasites. Moreover, prodigiosin–metal nanoparticle combinations reduced IC₅₀ values by 2.7–3.6 fold without increasing mammalian cell toxicity, suggesting the promise of microbial pigment-based nanocarriers (Rahul et al., 2015).

Violacein-loaded poly(d,l-lactide-co-glycolide) nanoparticles coated with L-ascorbic acid were developed for controlled release studies. The pigment was released in a stepwise manner at different rates, and these nanoparticles exhibited a twofold higher antitumor effect compared to free violacein (Martins et al., 2010).

To evaluate anticancer potential, violacein-loaded β -cyclodextrin-thiol–gold nanoparticles were synthesized and tested on V79 and HL60 cell lines. MTT assays showed that these nanoparticles preserved the cytotoxic activity of violacein against HL60 cells while exhibiting lower toxicity toward normal V79 cells compared to free violacein (Gimenez et al., 2006).

Understanding the molecular basis of apoptosis is an important goal in cancer research (Bilici et al., 2025). The antileukemic activity of L-ascorbic acid and violacein-loaded PAMAM dendrimer was investigated in Jurkat E6.1 (human acute lymphoblastic leukemia) cells. MTT assay demonstrated that the dendrimer–violacein complex (IC₅₀ = 4 μ M) was approximately twofold more effective compared to free violacein. Flow cytometry analysis revealed that caspase-3, -7, and -8 induced apoptosis in 29%, 34%, and 41% of cells, respectively. The authors suggested that the higher uptake of ascorbic acid by cancer cells makes this system a promising candidate for targeted drug delivery and reduction of side effects (Fakhr et al., 2012). In another study, violacein was encapsulated into nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) composed of solid lipid (myristyl myristate), a mixture of capric and caprylic acids, and the

surfactant Poloxamer P188. Cytotoxicity assays conducted on A549 and HCT-116 cancer cell lines demonstrated strong anticancer activity, attributed to the mucoadhesive chitosan matrix, and highlighted the synergistic biological effects of violacein and lipase (Berti et al., 2023).

Violacein-loaded nanostructured lipid carriers (VIO-NLCs) were prepared for anti-acne applications using the melt-emulsification technique. VIO-NLCs at 2% concentration demonstrated the ability to inhibit the growth of *Cutibacterium acnes* ATCC 6919 for up to 60 days during the incubation period. In addition, VIO-NLCs at 2% were found to exhibit inhibitory effects against *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 12228 throughout a storage period of 30 days (Leelaudomlipi et al., 2021).

Conclusion

Violacein, owing to its versatile biological activities, has emerged as a valuable biopigment with both pharmaceutical and industrial significance (Choi et al., 2015). However, its low solubility and bioavailability have limited its therapeutic potential (Durán et al., 2007). Findings from the literature indicate that nanocarrier systems can substantially overcome these limitations. Polymeric nanoparticles, lipid-based carriers, chitosan-derived structures, combinations with metal nanoparticles, and supramolecular complexes have been reported to enhance violacein solubility, reduce toxic side effects, and provide controlled release capabilities (Martins et al., 2011; Mohd et al., 2019; Rahul et al., 2015).

Moreover, the observation that violacein-loaded nanocomplexes do not induce toxicity in normal cells while mitigating adverse effects is of considerable importance. Critical obstacles to cancer treatment are drug insensitivity and resistance (Bilici and Akkoç, 2025). Notably, reports of synergistic activities in antimicrobial and anticancer effects suggest that violacein could serve as a promising lead molecule for the development of multi-target therapeutic agents in the future (Asencio et al., 2014). Nevertheless, several barriers remain before clinical translation can be achieved. The long-term effects of violacein on healthy cells and the microbiome are still insufficiently elucidated (Durán et al., 2007; Kodach et al., 2006). Additionally, issues such as the scalability of different nanocarrier systems, production costs, and regulatory frameworks are still under investigation. Therefore, future research should focus both on elucidating the pharmacokinetic profile of violacein and on ensuring the safety and reliability of nanocarrier platforms.

In conclusion, nanotechnology-enabled delivery of violacein underscores its potential as a strong candidate for next-generation antimicrobial and anticancer therapeutic strategies. However, comprehensive, multicenter in vivo and clinical studies are required to fully assess its impacts on human health and the environment.

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